

Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some Lanthanide(III) Ions with Schiff Bases derived from some 2-Aminothiazoles and Salicylaldehyde

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Manuscript received 21 May 1987, revised 29 January 1988,
accepted 19 February 1988

THE present communication deals with the determination of stability constants for the interaction of lanthanide(III) ions (La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy and Ho) with the Schiff bases derived from 2-aminothiazole or 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and salicylaldehyde.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: 2-Salicylaldiminothiazole (SB₁) and 2-salicylaldimino-4-phenylthiazole (SB₂) were synthesised¹ by the interaction of salicylaldehyde with the respective aminothiazoles.

A 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture was used as solvent for equilibrium studies. Rare earth perchlorates were prepared by dissolving the corresponding oxides (A.R.) in perchloric acid. pH measurements were carried out at 20° (±0.1°) with a ECIL 823 expanded scale pH meter (accuracy ±0.05) using glass electrodes in nitrogen atmosphere. CO₂-free sodium hydroxide was used as titrant. The stability constants were determined following the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{2,3} as adapted by Irving and Rossotti⁴. The calculations were done on a DEC-2050 computer by least-square method. The results are depicted in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS

Protonation constant	Metal(III) ion	Formation constant		
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
SB ₁ pK _a ^H = 3.95 pK ₁ ^H = 12.00	La	6.92	6.52	6.13
	Pr	7.13	6.92	6.85
	Nd	7.23	7.03	6.90
	Sm	7.53	7.42	7.17
	Eu	7.70	7.42	7.23
	Gd	7.57	7.32	7.20
	Tb	8.02	7.48	7.29
	Dy	8.37	7.69	7.46
SB ₂ pK _a ^H = 3.92 pK ₁ ^H = 11.74	La	7.18	6.61	6.00
	Pr	7.28	6.84	6.29
	Nd	7.44	6.92	6.32
	Sm	7.64	6.97	6.52
	Eu	7.88	7.10	6.70
	Gd	7.73	7.02	6.60
	Tb	7.99	7.20	6.77
	Dy	8.77	7.92	7.58
Ho	8.88	8.10	7.80	

Results and Discussion

The identical nature of the formation curves determined from the ligand-metal ratios of 5:1 and 25:1 ruled out the possibility of formation of polynuclear species. The highest value of $\bar{n} \approx 3$ indicated the combining ratio of metal-ligand as 1:3. The rare earth metal ions binds predominantly to oxygen and weakly to nitrogen. Parallel to the reported trend^{5,6}, a regular increase of stability constants was observed from lanthanum to holmium with the exception of gadolinium due to the combined effect of ligand field stabilisation and the hydration number of the metal ions. The chelate formation also contributes to the greater stability of the present complexes.

References

- O. L. SHARMA and V. MISHRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1986, **16**, 243.
- BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", 2nd. ed., P. Haase, Copenhagen, 1957.
- M. CALVIN and K. W. J. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2008.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3994; 1954, 2904.
- R. SCHWARZENBACH, R. GUT and G. ANDERROG, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, **37**, 987.
- R. HARDER and S. CHARBERK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 197.

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 4,8-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl-coumarins

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Anantapur-515 003Manuscript received 9 December 1987, revised 7 March 1988,
accepted 21 March 1988

COUMARIN and coumarin compounds are reported to possess various physiological activities¹. In our earlier studies² we found an increase in the bacteriological properties of the coumarins by introducing various substituted-alkyl/aryl-aminomethyl linkages at various positions of coumarin nucleus. In the present investigation, we report the synthesis and the antibacterial activity of 4,8-dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethylcoumarins.

4,8-Dimethylcoumarin³ and 4,8-dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin⁴ are prepared by the reported method. 4,8-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethylcoumarins (3) are prepared by condensing 4,8-dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin with various substituted-amines in dry benzene. The compounds were characterised from their elemental as well as

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spectral studies. The ir spectra of 3 showed peaks at 1 704–1 722 (lactone carbonyl), 2 875–2 950 (methyl C–H), 1 176–1 275 (C–N) and 3 300–3 450 cm^{-1} (N–H in the case of compounds prepared using primary amines). The ^1H nmr spectra of 3 showed a 2-proton peak at δ 4.45–4.48 corresponding to the methylene group of amino function, and the other peaks were observed at δ 2.40–2.50 (3H, s, C_6 – CH_3), 2.45–2.60 (3H, s, C_4 – CH_3) and 7.1–7.5 (3H, m, C_5 –H, C_6 –H, and C_7 –H).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaris on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

4,8-Dimethyl-3-(p-tolyl)aminomethylcoumarin (3a): 4,8-Dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin (2; 0.5 g) was refluxed with *p*-toluidine (0.6 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) on a steam-bath for 4 h. Benzene was then removed by vacuum distillation and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol as yellow shining needles (60%), m.p. 166–67° (Found: C, 77.22; H, 6.42; N, 4.74. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires: C, 77.84; H, 6.48; N, 4.77%); λ_{max} (EtOH) ($\log \epsilon$) 225 (3.89) and 375 nm (4.62); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 361 (N–H), 2 840–2 960 (Ar– CH_3), 1 704 (lactone C=O), 1 500–1 600 (Ar C=C), 1 183 and 1 268 (C–N).

Similarly, the other title compounds (3b–n) were prepared (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity of the compounds (3a–n) were screened *in vitro* against *Xanthomonas citri*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas viticola* by paper-disc method⁵.

TABLE 1—4,8-DIMETHYL-3-SUBSTITUTED-AMINOMETHYL-COUMARINS (3a–n)

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
3a	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	166–67	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3b	Morpholine		125–28	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$
3c	Methyl	Phenyl	124	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3d	<i>n</i> -Butyl	<i>n</i> -Butyl	220–23	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3e	2-Phenylindolyl		98–100	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3f	H	6-(4-Methylpyridyl)	186–38	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$
3g	H	6-(2-Methylpyridyl)	155–57	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$
3h	H	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	178–80	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3i	3,5-Dimethylpyrazolyl		180–32	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$
3j	H	Phenyl	162–64	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3k	Ethyl	Phenyl	170–72	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3l	H	1-Naphthyl	206–07	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3m	Benzyl	Benzyl	258–60	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$
3n		Piperidine	118–14	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$

*Satisfactory C, H and N analysis obtained.

The standard antibacterial drug used was sulphamamide. The zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the paper-disc was measured. The screening results (Table 2) indicate that some of the compounds possess higher activity and some moderate to no activity against some of the bacteria. The compounds which possess higher activity are 4,8-dimethyl-3,6-(4-methylpyridyl)coumarin (3f) against *X. citri* and *P. viticola*, and 4,8-dimethyl-3,6-(2-methylpyridyl)coumarin (3g) against *X. citri* and *B. subtilis*. From the above results it can be inferred that the introduction of picolinylamino linkage enhances the activity of coumarin nucleus.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 1, 2 AND 3a–n

Compd. no.	<i>X. citri</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. viticola</i>
1	–	+	–	+
2	+	+	+	+
3a	+	–	+	–
3b	+	+	–	+
3c	+	–	–	+
3d	–	–	–	+
3e	+	+	+	–
3f	++	+	+	++
3g	++	++	+	+
3h	+	–	–	–
3i	+	+	+	+
3j	+	+	+	+
3k	–	–	+	–
3l	+	–	–	+
3m	–	–	+	–
3n	+	+	–	–

*Zone dia: (+) = <10 mm, (++) = >10 mm, (–) = no inhibition.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. R. Ramanjaneyulu, Department of Microbiology, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur for screening the compounds for antibacterial activity, and grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (M.N.).

References

1. G. FEUER in "Progress in Medicinal Chemistry", ed. G. P. ELLIS and G. B. WEST, North-Holland Publishing Company, New York, 1974.
2. A. K. RAO, M. S. RAJU and K. M. RAJU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1021, G. SAILAJA, K. M. RAJU and M. S. RAJU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, **24**, 206; M. NAGESAM, M. S. RAJU and K. M. RAJU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 418, M. NAGESAM, K. M. RAJU and M. S. RAJU, *Indian J. Phar. Soc.*, 1988, **50**, 49.
3. B. K. GANGULY and P. BAGCHI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1415.
4. K. M. JAINAMMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 985.
5. A. A. DEAN, "Laboratory Instruction in Microbiology", Mosby Company, London, 1974.

- 7, R=CH₃, R₁=CH₃, n=1 10; R=CH₃, R₁=SCH₃, n=2
 8; R=C₆H₅, R₁=CH₃, n=1 11; R=C₆H₅, R₁=SCH₃, n=2
 9, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=CH₃, n=1
 12, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=SCH₃, n=2

- 13, R=CH₃, R₁=R₂=H 16; R=CH₃, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃
 14; R=C₆H₅, R₁=R₂=H 17; R=C₆H₅, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃
 15, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=R₂=H
 18; R=CH₂CH=CH₂, R₁=OH, R₂=CH₃

Synthesis of some Carboxyalkyl- and Pyrimidyl-substituted-thiocarbamides as Potential Fungicides and Nematicides

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Manuscript received 1 April 1987, revised 8 February 1988, accepted 11 March 1988

SOME work has been reported on thiocarbamides and substituted-thiocarbamides with regards to their complexing ability, ionisation constants and fungicidal activities¹. The interest in the derivatives of thiocarbamides with heterodonor atoms with respect to their complexing ability, ionisation constants, fungicidal activity is of recent origin².

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Isothiocyanates were prepared by usual methods³. The substituted-thiocarbamides, viz. *N*-methyl- (1), *N*-phenyl- (2) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(1,5-dicarboxypropyl)thiocarbamide (3); *N*-methyl-(4), *N*-phenyl- (5) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(1,4-dicarboxyethyl)-thiocarbamide (6); *N*-methyl- (7), *N*-phenyl- (8) and

- 1, R=CH₃, n=2 4, R=OH₂, n=1
 2, R=C₆H₅, n=2 5, R=C₆H₅, n=1
 3, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, n=2 6, R=CH₂CH=CH₂, n=1

N-allyl-*N'*-(carboxyethyl)thiocarbamide (9); bis-*N*-methyl- (10), bis-*N*-phenyl- (11) and bis-*N*-allyl-*N'*-(carboxyethylthio)thiocarbamide (12) were prepared as follows. A solution of the isothiocyanate (methyl, phenyl or allyl; 0.05 mol) was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol, and amino acid (glutamic acid, aspartic acid, alanine or cystine; 0.05 mol) in 1N NaOH (100 ml). Both the solutions were mixed and stirred at room temperature for 48 h. The solution was then filtered, cooled in an ice-bath and acidified with HCl (1:1). The resulting solid (substituted-thiocarbamide) was washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol.

N-Methyl- (13), *N*-phenyl- (14) and *N'*-allyl-*N'*-(2-pyrimidyl)thiocarbamide (15); *N*-methyl- (16), *N*-phenyl- (17) and *N*-allyl-*N'*-(4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidyl)thiocarbamide (18) were prepared as follows. To a solution of 2-aminopyrimidine (0.5 mol) in minimum quantity of ethanol, or to a solution of 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine (0.5 mol) in minimum quantity of ethanol-water mixture 50% (v/v), an equal amount of the isothiocyanate (methyl, phenyl or allyl) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h and cooled when crystals of substituted-pyrimidylthiocarbamides separated out which were recrystallised from ethanol. Uv spectra (EtOH) of the thiocarbamides were taken on a UV-VIS PMQ3 spectrophotometer. The transition energy (*E_T*) and molar extinction coefficient *ε*_{max} were calculated by using standard equations. *R_T* values of the thiocarbamides in ethyl acetate-benzene and ethyl acetate-carbon tetrachloride were calculated (Table 1). Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) of these thiocarbamides were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The carboxyalkyl-substituted-thiocarbamides show absorption maxima at 200-210 and 260-275